

WHO IS THIS JOURNALIST? WHAT DOES A REAL JOURNALIST LOOK LIKE?

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6791903>

Abstract. *Who is a journalist? In this regard, globally, he is a professional who can become a professional, and who sacrifices his life for a small profession. Journalism is evolving rapidly these days as a profession. We live in a world with a fast flow of information. Numerous various magazines and newspapers appeared. Various universities offer regular journalism courses. Journalism is currently attracting many talented and gifted students.*

Key words: *journalism, communication, press, radio, television, news agencies, photography, cinematography.*

КТО ЭТОТ ЖУРНАЛИСТ? КАК ВЫГЛЯДИТ НАСТОЯЩИЙ ЖУРНАЛИСТ?

Аннотация. *Кто такой журналист? В этом плане глобально он профессионал, который может стать профессионалом, и который жертвует своей жизнью ради маленькой профессии. В наши дни журналистика как профессия стремительно развивается. Мы живем в мире с быстрым потоком информации. Появилось множество различных журналов и газет. Различные университеты предлагают регулярные курсы журналистики. Журналистика в настоящее время привлекает много талантливых и одаренных студентов.*

Ключевые слова: *журналистика, общение, пресса, радио, телевидение, информационные агентства, фотография, кинематография.*

INTRODUCTION

Journalism is a type of social activity. The owners (journalists) collect, analyze and disseminate socially relevant information through the press, radio, television, news agencies and others. Journalism is a form of mass propaganda. The nature and purpose of journalism depend on the social nature of the society. The term journalism was first applied to a collection of journals, and later to all periodicals. The term journalism now refers to the product of journalism, a set of related professions, as well as education and science in that field. Journalistic activities include the press, radio, television, news agencies, documentaries and others.

The media in journalism relies heavily on journalism to meet the public's need for up-to-date social and specialized information, as well as scientific, artistic, and other works that address important social issues. The media in a journalistic system operates at a certain frequency and speed.

The first buds of social activity aimed at collecting, analyzing, and disseminating information date back to antiquity. Informing people about social events and influencing them through the media has taken many forms and methods. Oral information was provided by speakers and announcers. Written information was written and distributed on papyrus in ancient Egypt. In ancient Rome, advertisements and manuscripts were used.

DISCUSSION

Modern Journalism first appeared in the form of the first periodicals of the early seventeenth century. In the second half of the nineteenth century and in the twentieth century, thanks to the invention of photography and cinematography, photography and film journalism were formed. From the twentieth century onwards, radio journalism began to develop on the basis of the achievements of radio engineering, and in the 1940s, television journalism emerged. With the emergence and development of the media, the need for journalists with a high level of generality and professionalism has increased. It was this need that led to the creation of special "Journalism" education in different countries. There are several types of journalism that differ in their political orientation, and there are different views on the role and function of journalism in public life. In particular, the activities of communist journalism were based on partisanship and class. This has in many cases led to the restriction and gross violation of human rights and freedoms in the field of information in a universal sense.

The development of journalism depends on a number of factors, including political freedoms and, in particular, freedom of the press. Freedom of the press is a necessary condition for the development of a democratic society. Only in the conditions of free activity can a journalist provide objective and truthful information to the members of the society and act as a mediator between the state and the society.

Journalism in Uzbekistan appeared in the second half of the 19th century. Its history begins with official periodicals such as the *Turkestanskiye Vedomosti* and the *Turkistan Region Newspaper*, published in Tashkent. In the first and second decades of the twentieth century, private national newspapers and magazines "Taraqqiy", "Khurshid", "Sadoi Turkiston", "Samarkand", "Oyina" and others were published in Uzbekistan, focusing on educating educated people capable of ensuring national development. During the Soviet era, the periodical network in Uzbekistan expanded to include national, regional, and district political and network newspapers, as well as new magazines, as well as radio and television journalism in Uzbekistan. However, they were doomed to serve the political, economic and ideological goals of the dictatorship.

THE RESULT

After the independence of Uzbekistan, the republic's journalism entered a democratic stage, and a new system began to take shape, which helped to democratize the society and build a democratic state based on the rule of law. 1997, "On Guarantees and Freedom of Information," The Law on Protection of Journalism and the Law on Mass Media were adopted. Also, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 26, 1999 "On improving the system of training and retraining of journalists" was published. These documents are of great importance in improving the system of training and retraining of journalists in our country and raising them to the level of world standards. Much has been done since then to implement these laws and decisions. As a result of independence, the approach of the republic's journalists to the analysis and coverage of social events has changed radically. Journalists now rely on scientific knowledge, universal and national values, and universally recognized democratic principles in their analysis and coverage of social processes.

In the process of formation of the journalism system, special higher education in journalism was established in the republic. In 1949, a special department for the training of journalists with higher education was established at the Faculty of Philology of the Central Asian State University. In 1967, the department was transformed into an independent faculty. By the

resolution of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan (April 26, 1996) the honorary title of "Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was established. Journalists with higher education The Uzbek University of Journalism and Mass Communications was established by the Presidential Decree of May 24, 2018. The Tashkent branch, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies, Silk Road International Tourism University also train in the field of Travel journalism. Since 1997, the International Social Center for Retraining Journalists has been operating at the Academy of State and Social Construction under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSION

Obviously, we can't imagine today without news. Television, radio, press and the Internet are the foundations of journalism. So, journalism is important in everyone's life. Understanding the true history and potential of this field is the first and most important step in entering the field of journalism. In today's rapidly evolving media space, the field of journalism and the role of the journalist are growing.

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